

Introduction: Conflict in the contemporary rural world. New interpretations of an old problem

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The peasantry: a contemporary historical subject

One of the characteristics of this monographic issue of *Workers of the World* is that we conceived of and attempted to explore the history of peasants and farmers as rural *workers* and also as pluriactive or “symbiotic” agents, capable of influencing and adapting to contemporary processes of social and productive transformation.² We expressed this clearly in the *Call for Papers*. The other characteristic is that we tried to organize a global edition and we achieved it in part, with the presence of works from two continents and seven different national states, although in terms of the peasantry we may refer to twelve distinct geographic territories covered in the edition since the peasantry does not define state boundaries nor does it conform to them. Indeed, it pressures and pluralizes state boundaries.

A central and traditional object of study in the field of the history of social conflicts, and social history as a whole, has undoubtedly been the working class, often understood as “working classes” precisely because of its plurality and diversity of conditions, rather than being seen as a homogeneous social group. The initial analyses in the field of social history predominantly paid attention to the lives and work of industrial workers and the organization of labour in countries that were considered to be “advanced

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² There is a great deal of literature regarding the industrial, commercial, and daily activities of the peasantry. An excellent guide is DOMINGUEZ MARTÍN, Rafael. “Caracterizando al campesinado y a la economía campesina: pluriactividad y dependencia del mercado como nuevos atributos de la “campesinidad”. *Agricultura y Sociedad*. n. 66, 1993, 97-136. As for adaptation and unrest, some perspectives that guided our work had already been raised by ARTIAGA, Aurora; BALBOA, Xesús L; CARDESIN, J.M.; FERNÁNDEZ PRIETO, L.; HERVÉS, Henrique. “Agricultura y capitalismo en Galicia. Una perspectiva histórica”. In: VILLARES, R. and SAAVEDRA, P. eds., *Señores y Campesinos en la Península Ibérica (ss. XVIII-XX)*. Barcelona: Crítica, vol. 2, 1991 and HERVÉS, Henrique; FERNÁNDEZ GONZÁLEZ, A.; FERNÁNDEZ PRIETO, L; ARTIAGA, Aurora; BALBOA, Xesús L. “Resistencia y organización. La conflictividad rural en Galicia desde la crisis del Antiguo Régimen al franquismo”. *Historia Agraria*. 13, 1997, pp. 165-191. And following this Hispanic thread of rural studies, an important inspiration came from SEVILLA-GUZMÁN, E. and GONZÁLEZ DE MOLINA, M. *Ecología, campesinado e Historia*. Madrid: Eds. de la Piqueta, 1993.

capitalist”, of which the English case featured as the genuine model. Yet the progressive historiographical renewal of the second half of the twentieth century assisted in diversifying, on the one hand, the objects of study, and, on the other, it helped to break with interpretative paradigms of a more deterministic and teleological character.

The deficiencies were marked in part by some of the positions of Marx himself, which left a lasting impression on the historiography of the left.³ Both classical Marxism, from a theoretical point of view, and the political parties and the trade unions whose practice was inspired by it, had difficulties dealing with the integration of the peasantry in their readings of capitalist social relations and their alternatives to overcome them. Marx dismissed the question of the attitudes and potential for social transformation of the peasantry with the successful (for its repercussion, not for its accuracy) expression “sack of potatoes”. The ties of the peasantry to the land it farmed, its immediate surroundings, its supposed individualism, the mirage of property (whether real or as an aspiration) and its apparent isolation hampered the collective actions of the peasantry. It is significant, in this sense, that the depth, subtlety and nuance of Marx’s analysis of capitalism and the proletariat was not matched by his analysis of the peasantry and agriculture. The conception of the peasantry as a dead weight, incapable of adding value to any revolutionary process, led Marxists to downplay its importance in their interpretation of reality, as they predicted the drastic decline in the agricultural workforce as a consequence of the unstoppable progress of industrial capitalism. If the means of production developed as they had been intended to in this Marxist interpretation, we would thus observe in agriculture the same process of concentration that had already occurred in the industrial sector (concentration of capital, decrease of the craft sector, etc.), which would give rise to corporately managed large farms. The fate of the peasants was either emigration or exodus to the cities to reinforce the needs of the secondary sector, thus becoming real proletarians. Coinciding with conceptions in classical economics, the economic role of agriculture as a sector would be subordinated as a mere supplier of food and, in the process of primitive accumulation, a provider of capital and labour.

With the development of the labour movement in the late nineteenth century, the European socialist parties (as well as the trade unions) would face the problems that arose from this discourse when they needed to propagandize and mobilize for collective actions in rural areas. Both the agriculture and peasantry still had an enormous weight in the European economies and societies at the turn of the century. Furthermore, the data did not corroborate the Marxist prediction of the decline of the small peasantry since family farming had weathered with surprising adaptability the broad, baffling agrarian crisis at the end of the century, capable of shaking up the agricultural estates and consciences throughout Europe. Moreover, the crisis also inflicted serious damage on large farms, affected by the rise in wages and by the exclusive dependency on certain cash crops.

The practical difficulties that these theoretical standpoints meant for the expansion of socialism in rural areas led to intense debates at the core of social democracy,

³ F. Engels had similar positions. For example, in *The Peasant War in Germany* (1850) and *The Peasant Question in France and Germany* (1894).

particularly within German social democracy.⁴ This controversy was related to, but did not overlap with, the debate over revolution and revisionism. Kautsky emerged as the guardian of orthodoxy (years later he would revise his positions): to defend the small landholding peasant was to prolong the agony of a social group doomed to extinction that was also fundamentally “counter-revolutionary”. In the case of the Italian Socialist Party, the only European socialist party with a strong agricultural base, its expansion was largely due to the figure most easily assimilated by the proletariat, the rural labourer (*bracciante*) in need of land to work on and whose demands (greater salary, reduction in working hours, etc.) and methods used to achieve them (strikes) were comparable to those of industrial workers. However, Italian socialism was unable to incorporate in equal measure the needs and traditions (mutual support and reduction of the recruitment of wage labour) of the other categories within the peasantry, leading to the tragic consequences of the fascist offensive in 1921-22.⁵ Throughout Europe, the difficulties of the socialist parties were very similar⁶ and in the absence of a reassessment of theoretical dogmas, cooperativism in its multiple forms (on which were pinned the hopes of spreading collective habits which would erode the supposed individualism of the peasants) was the main palliative.

The more militant, and increasingly theoretically stagnant, Marxist historiography continued to voice these positions until after the Second World War. The lack of cooperation of the peasantry with the labour movement was attributed to their alleged lack of class-consciousness and inability to shake off the mental and material shackles of traditional hierarchies (landowners, clergy, etc.). In the 1960s new perspectives began to emerge, especially British cultural Marxism. E. P. Thompson was able to understand the logic of seemingly *primitive* actions like the food riots of eighteenth century England, while contributing to *dematerialize* the analysis of such conflicts. These were no longer exclusively due to the evolution of objective and measurable factors (prices, wages, distribution of land), but also due to the cultural values associated with the economic activity, and the expectations regarding what was to be expected of the different actors involved, which Thompson coined the “moral economy.” Meanwhile Hobsbawm and Rude, in their study of the Captain Swing riots, revalued the rational logic of actions that had traditionally been dismissively referred to as simple fury against “progress”.⁷

⁴ LEHMANN, H-G-. *Die Agrarfrage in der Theorie und Praxis der deutschen und internationalen Sozialdemokratie*. Tübingen: J. C. B. Mohr, 1970.

⁵ See PROCCACCI. *La lotta di classe in Italia agli inizi del secolo XX*. Roma: Editori Riuniti Procacci, 1972 for a classic vision and CRAINZ, G.. *Padania: Il mondo dei braccianti dall'Ottocento alla fuga dalle campagne*. Roma: Donzelli Editore, 1994 for a revision that shows how the *braccianti*, even those who were socialist militants, had not necessarily renounced the aspiration of private ownership of the land nor had they left behind the peasant ethos. There was a certain parallelism in the clash in France between BARRAL, P. *Les Agrariens français de Méline à Pisani*. Paris : A. Colin, 1968 and BARRAL, Pierre and GRATTON, P. *Les Paysans française contre l'agrarianisme*. Paris: Editions François Maspero, 1972. Barral put the emphasis of the involvement of the French peasantry in the political sphere around the nineteenth century on associationism and Gratton replied that the “agrarian defense” discourse only benefited the powerful and hid the class struggle that in the rural world included lumberjacks, day labourers, etc.

⁶ BLOK, A; HITCHINS, Keith; MARKEY, Raymond; SIMONSON, Birgir. eds., *Urban radicals, rural allies. Social Democracy and the Agrarian Issue, 1870-1914*. Bern: Peter Lang, 2002.

⁷ HOBBSAWM, E. J.; RUDÉ, G.. *Captain Swing: A Social History of the Great English Agricultural Uprising of 1830*. New York, Pantheon Books, 1969.

Hobsbawm would also rescue the role of the peasantry in socio-political processes, although his theoretical positions would lead him to qualify as "primitive" the formulas and ideologies separate from Marxism, as in the case of Andalusian anarchism.⁸

There was also a reevaluation of the role of the peasantry in historical sociology such as Charles Tilly's work on the defensive or reactive conflicts to keep the state at bay (which for Tilly was the vanguard of economic progress and modernization in general), giving way to proactive conflicts in which influence within the political and administrative system was sought.⁹ And although his conclusions were controversial, since they seemed to imply that a precondition for the triumph of liberal democracy was a reduction, as drastic as possible, of the peasantry, another historical sociologist Barrington Moore also put the fundamental role of the peasantry on the table, showing that its political positions could decide one way or another the outcome of the struggle between democracy, fascism and communism.¹⁰

Thompson, Hobsbawm, Rude and Tilly, among many others, contributed to this renewal that would also result in a rethinking of the significance of the processes of politicization, until that time closely associated with what were considered certain essential moments and historical subjects, almost as if there were "chosen" classes. In the consolidation of these new perspectives, a key aspect was the criticism of modernization theories, which had gained a hegemonic status in the social sciences since World War II. So much so that social science and modernization theories constituted an essential part of an era and a paradigm: that of modernization. It was in this context that the social sciences were constructed and their arguments strengthened: through studying the delay and obstacles to modernizing development. What about history? Imbued with such social scientific theories, researchers regarded history as the best place to discover how obstacles to progress developed. The past was effectively turned into a laboratory of modernization in the present.

Following this historiographical renewal, but in a more focused manner, the rural world and its protagonists, the peasants, would later become central objects of attention. When investigating the composition of the British working class in the Industrial Revolution – and "industrialization" before the Industrial Revolution itself – there was nothing to be found, but the rural world and peasants. But that was in the past. In the present of Thompson, Hobsbawm and Rude in the 1950s and 1960s, the prominence obtained by farmers in the context of the liberation struggles of the Third World put the emphasis on the need to diversify beyond a Eurocentric and industrial-urban perspective. In this second half of the twentieth-century, peasants were no longer considered as the "sack of potatoes" defined by Marx in the nineteenth-century, useless to the revolution that only the working class could undertake. To the contrary, they began to appear as

⁸ HOBBSBWM, E. J. *Primitive Rebels. Archaic Forms of Social Movement in the 19th and 20th Centuries*. Manchester, Manchester University Press, 1959; HOBBSBWM, E. J. *Bandits*. London: Penguin Books, 1972.

⁹ TILLY, C. *The contentious French. Four Centuries of Popular Struggle*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1986.

¹⁰ MOORE, B. *Social Origins of Dictatorship and Democracy. Lord and Peasant in the Making of the Modern World*. London: Beacon Press, 1966.

active social and political agents in the liberation and anti-colonial struggles of the Third World, as shown by the studies of E. Wolf and J.M. Paigne.¹¹

The contemporary realities of the 1970s allowed such scholars to see a different past when reviewing classic themes. It also opened space for a dialogue with the parallel conceptualizations of the peasantry as defined by rural anthropologists and sociologists, from the Polish rural sociology of the 1920s to the fundamental contributions of peasant studies led by T. Shanin and passing through the conceptualizations and reconceptualizations of anthropologists such as Kroeber from 1923-1948 and E.J. Wolf in 1966.¹² The appearance on both sides of the Atlantic (USA and UK) of the *Journal of Peasant Studies* in the early 1970s represented a concrete materialization of this new research on the peasantry in which anthropologists, historians and sociologists participated (as did the World Bank, politicians and university students). Farmers got "trendy" and the search for conceptual categories and theories that could bring us closer to the understanding of its historical evolution and its role in history led not only to new formulations, but reinterpretations of classic authors such as Lenin and Redfield.¹³ In this context, the rediscovery of the Russian author Alexander Chayanov in the 1960s was fundamental; especially his studies from the 1920s on the workings of the peasant economy – the peasant economic unit – that he had actually begun before the Russian Revolution of 1917.¹⁴ During the Russian Revolution, Chayanov developed his understanding of the nature and logic of the peasantry and published *Peasant Farm Organization* in 1925 in which he formalized and revealed the economic aspects of the peasant family. This Russian populist and independent socialist, convicted in the Stalinist purges of 1930 and executed in 1937, has since been instrumental to peasant studies and to the understanding of the relationship of the peasantry to the market and to wages.¹⁵

But this renewal of peasant studies emerged through a long and often interrupted process. Under the modernization paradigm in European and Western history itself, it was revealed that the history of rural areas and peasants was generally relegated to a secondary

¹¹ WOLF, E. *Peasant Wars in the Twentieth Century*. London: Faber and Faber, 1969; PAIGNE, J.M. *Agrarian Revolution: social movements and export agriculture in the Underdeveloped World*. New York: Free Press, 1975.

¹² KROEBER, A.L. *Anthropology: race, language, culture, psychology, pre-history*. New York: Harcourt-Brace, 1948; WOLF, E. *Peasants*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall, 1966.

¹³ LENIN, V.I. *Development of Capitalism in Russia The Process of the Formation of a Home Market for Large-Scale Industry*. Moscow: Progress Publishers, 1977 [1899]; REDFIELD, R. *The Little Community*. Chicago, University of Chicago Press, 1956; *Peasant Society*, Chicago, Chicago University Press, 1956.

¹⁴ CHAYANOV, A. *La organización de la explotación campesina La organización de la unidad económica campesina*. Buenos Aires: Ediciones Nueva Visión, 1974 [1925].

¹⁵ The first publication of Chayanov in English appeared in SOROKIN, P.A.; ZIMMERMAN, C.C.; GALPPIN, C.J. *Systematic Source Book of Rural Sociology*. New York: Russell & Russell, 1965. In 1966, his *magnum opus* was published. CHAYANOV, A. In: KERBLAY, B; SMITH, R.E.F. and THORNER, D. eds., *Theory of the Peasant Economy*. Homewood, Ill.: Richard D. Irwin for the American Economics Association, 1966. A Spanish edition followed in 1974. See CHAYANOV, A. *La organización de la unidad económica campesina*. *Op.Cit.* The last two publications recovered the two most important books by Chayanov from the 1920s *Sobre la teoría de los sistemas económicos no-capitalistas* and *La organización de la explotación campesina*. The English version of 1966 was translated from the German and the Spanish version of 1974 from Russian. See SÁNCHEZ DE PUERTA TRUJILO, F. *La economía de trabajo (Alexander Vasilevich Chayanov: Selección de escritos)*. *Agricultura y Sociedad*. n. 55, 1990, pp. 239-248.

role, limited to occasional outbursts of protest arising from their poor living conditions or rejection of the innovations of modernity. Groups of farmers became peripheral, ostracized, quintessentially subordinated groups, incapable even of revolt against historiography. Not surprisingly, the contemporary world started, symbolically, with the French Revolution and the struggle of the Jacobins against the "reactionary" peasants of the Vendée. Throughout modernity, peasants had been the repositories of reaction, of political conservatism and, in some cases, the essence of patriotic traditions that were lost in the mists of time, unable even to support or collaborate with the historically revolutionary classes of modernity, whether it be the bourgeoisie or, later, the proletariat. The farmers were the Irish scabs of Marx's England, or the tireless workers of the "cursed races" of his son-in-law, P. Lafargue, in *The Right to be Lazy*.¹⁶

Therefore, concepts such as "democracy", "citizenship" or simply "politics" let alone technological innovation or social change were incompatible with the nature of social processes related to the rural world.¹⁷ These ideas dominated in some influential theories of political science in the second half of the twentieth century, which generally pushed in two ways for a vision of politicization as a unidirectional process: from top to bottom (from the elites of the system to the public) and from the centre to the periphery (from the more modernized dimensions of the social system to the ones falling behind). Therefore, the politicization of the rural world was consistently conceived as a process of the incorporation of farmers into politics through a process of the arrival of a political reality that was completely foreign to them, and the only part they could play was in either accepting or rejecting these modern political identities.¹⁸ Precisely because of this, this paradigm may serve as the articulating element of this introduction since it rejects the peasantry as an object ("a sack of potatoes"), treating the peasants as subjects and actors in the process of democratization.¹⁹

Questioning the prejudiced vision of the peasantry thus signifies breaking with various interpretative inertias (which actually constituted a lasting interpretative model that was present all throughout modernity in the nineteenth and twentieth centuries). First, it is necessary to provide a two-way view of the processes of the politicization of the rural world, in which the rural world is not a passive subject of sociopolitical changes. This is an interpretation that favours the interaction between the adaptability of the elites of the system to the challenges posed by the demands of the political participation of the

¹⁶ LAFARGUE, P. *The Right to be Lazy*. Fifth Season Pr, 1999 [1883].

¹⁷ For an ample debate regarding changes in technology and the peasantry (farmers, ploughmen), consult PUJOL, J. and FERNÁNDEZ PRIETO, L. "El cambio tecnológico en la historia agraria de la España contemporánea". *Historia Agraria*. n. 24, August 2001, pp. 59-86. Another revisionist article is QUINTANA, X. R. "Campesinos que se adaptan agricultura que se mueve". *Áreas*. n. 12, 1990, pp. 147-165. For a monographic study with respect to this question, see FERNÁNDEZ PRIETO, L. *Labregos con ciencia. Estado, sociedad e innovación tecnológica na agricultura galega (1850-1939)*. Vigo: Eds. Xerais, 1992.

¹⁸ MACHO, Antonio Míguez; VILLAVARDE, Miguel Cabo. "Pisando la dudosa luz del día: el proceso de democratización en la Galicia rural de la Restauración". *Ayer*. n. 89, 2013, pp. 43-75.

¹⁹ MARKOFF, J. *Waves of democracy. Social Movements and Political Change*. Newbury Park, Ca., Pine Forge Press, 1996; MARKOFF, J. *The Abolition of Feudalism*. University Park, Penn.: State University of Pennsylvania, 1996.

peasantry, and the ability of the peasantry to influence and act in political struggles. Therefore, the statement by Hobsbawm, during the process of deagrarianization that was simultaneously going on in various parts of the world after the Second World War, that "the end of the Middle Ages" had arrived was also called into question.²⁰ The idea that nothing important had happened in the history of the rural world up to its extinction was false as was the stigma of backwardness, primitivism, social and technological millenarianism and immutability that it was blamed for. The ahistorical, purely imaginary, idea of a "traditional" and immutable world, either with no history or outside of it, should be strongly criticized.

It was in this way that the notion of "peasant logic" and the understanding of the rural world acquired a central role as a complex, changing and organic object of study. The peasants were understood as being able to articulate their discontent and their protests according to their own behavioural pattern, a prominent feature if one can see past the walls put up by theory of social movements which imposed a somewhat formalistic interpretation. On the other hand, the successful formula of James C. Scott's "weapons of the weak" was an explanation with Thompsonian foundations to the puzzle of how the peasants expressed their discontent while appearing submissive in the acceptance of their fate, and it did so by *empathizing* with their conditions (limits to formal organization, aversion to risk, social subordination, etc.).²¹ The combination of Scott's work with so called "subaltern studies", focused on colonial contexts, would be a catalyst for the study of the peasantry, which however still had to face criticism from Marxist positions that focused on the lack of definition of the subject, as well as accusations of populism.²²

Rude, Hobsbawm and H. Alavi, meanwhile, sought the peasant of their present in the past and found it as a pre-political and *primitive rebel*, capable of participating in riots, but not of creating policy proposals and even less capable of building civil society. What is remarkable is, in any case, the search, because the definition contains the explanation of a paradigm that is now too obsolete for us to keep using, even if it continues to appear and people persist on using it, whether because of the success of the expression or by virtue of the strength and intellectual authority of its authors or even simply by the powerful force of modernization theories in the explanation and understanding of present history. We are children of the welfare state, modernization and of the post-war years, as T. Judt demonstrated who, under the progressive influence of the *Annales*, did his thesis on contemporary French farmers.²³ However, a great deal of progress has been made in the characterization of peasants in history since then, and this progress is not without its importance for our knowledge of the past if we take into consideration that we are talking

²⁰ HOBBSAWM, Eric. *The Age of Extremes: The Short Twentieth Century, 1914–1991*. London: Michael Joseph, 1994, pp. 288–9, 415.

²¹ SCOTT, J.C. "Everyday Forms of Peasant Resistance". *Journal of Peasant Studies*. vol. 13, n. 2, 1986, pp. 5-35. See also SCOTT, J.C. *The moral economy of the peasant: Rebellion and subsistence in southeast Asia*. New Haven: Yale University Press, 1976 and *Domination and the Arts of Resistance. Hidden Transcripts*. New Haven: Yale University Press, 1990.

²² BRASS, T. *Peasants, Populism, and Post-modernism: The Return of the Agrarian Myth*. London: Frank Cass, 2000.

²³ JUDT, T. *Postwar. A History of Europe since 1945*. London: Penguin Press, 2006.

of the vast majority of humanity from the Neolithic period until well into the twentieth century. Even today peasants and farmers account for more than half the world's population.

Environmental studies also contributed to the task of conceptually redefining both the peasantry and its theoretical status. Authors such as Guha, Martínez Alier and Toledo have shown that the "lower classes" in the poorest of the poor countries, almost entirely constituted by farmers, largely indigenous, possess characteristics and knowledge worthy of being retrieved as they may hold the solution to the environmental crisis and help us achieve a more sustainable handling of agricultural ecosystems.²⁴ In this way, farmers lose their status of "waste" and gain a new status, that of an "alternative model", and they do so mostly under the eyes of non-Europeans. At the same time, this line of study that has become popular since the late twentieth century, has changed its outlook on the conflicts involving the peasantry, adding to their "logic" the defence of environmental ideals ("environmentalism of the poor", "popular environmentalism"), always starting from assumptions opposite to those of "enlightened" Western environmentalism.

The peasantry is a complex object of study, firstly, because the notion of "peasant" was revealed to be an abstraction of multiple realities and social identities that, although always taking place in the rural world, included various types of relationships to the land and to agricultural work. With respect to this, reference may be made to the debate on the definition of peasantry that occurred in the 1970s, which interacted with the crisis of structuralist Marxism. Beyond that, the complexity of analysis thrived with the increasing incorporation of other global realities outside the Western European context. A whole stream of studies related to rural realities in the so-called "Third World" found itself attached to the increased attention to environmental issues. The effects of the Green Revolution had reached a global dimension, constituting a project of transformation of the rural world in the context of the disturbing crisis of the environment and the sustainability of the model of development.

With respect to the idea of the changing subject, reference is made to the attention given to the historicity of the change in the rural world and its relation to society as a whole. The idea of the immutability of the peasantry and its environment, and its supposed secular isolation, was the result of a strongly ideological construction which was employed to justify the submission of their identity, to legitimate identity and romantic discourses on the building of European nations in the nineteenth century. It is actually a definition of the social sciences that opposes the urban with the rural, the modern with the traditional, the open market with autarchic-gated communities unfamiliar with the free movement of goods. Conceptions that established and served this paradigm of modernization and the development of the green revolution, although they were already present in the older attacks on the rustic world, reflected a view of the

²⁴ GUHA, R. "El ecologismo de los pobres". *Ecología Política*. n. 8, 1994, pp. 137-153; MARTÍNEZ ALIER, J. *El ecologismo de los pobres. Conflictos ambientales y lenguajes de valoración*. Barcelona: Icaria, 2004; TOLEDO, V. *La paz en Chiapas: Ecología, luchas indígenas y modernidad alternativa*. Chiapas, México: UNAM/Quinto Sol, 2000.

peasantry as ignorant and illiterate (a new version of the pagan) as opposed to the educated and enlightened urban world (a new version of Christianity) that began with the Enlightenment of the eighteenth century, and in some cases even before then.²⁵

The deconstruction of this discourse began with the analysis of some of its core elements, such as the evolution of social relations around the issue of land ownership. The complex process of peasant proprietarization went beyond merely overcoming feudalism and was interrelated with forms such as that of communal property that did not fit the "perfect" liberal and individual model of property. This went hand in hand with the new questionings of the alleged lack of technological renovation of the productive practices of peasants, which were traditionally subsumed under the dichotomy of mechanical *vs.* traditional agriculture. These new studies rather looked to include models of adaptation and "dead ends" that, again, challenged the unidirectionality of the notion of historical progress.

Finally, the very dynamics of this evolving and complex subject necessarily implied conflict. The rural world had been very much alive in history, and this was so primarily due to the capacity to organize themselves as one, to struggle for their interests when possible and to attempt to take advantage of what political and economic systems offered. The attempt to unify all these struggles under the category of "reactionary" resembled an ideological prejudice more than a historical observation, since this latter reality also demonstrated struggles to build profitable alternatives for the peasantry. The questioning of the model of development that prevailed through concepts such as modernization and progress also arose in this struggle for alternatives, directly or indirectly. In line with this approach, several authors have questioned the idea of a single genealogy of the concept of democracy in favour of a more plural and complex vision where the paths to democratization were numerous, although one eventually imposed itself.

The problem of the denomination of the peasantry, as we call it here in an attempt to unify academic studies in a comprehensive way, is not a minor problem. The denomination that has stood out has been that of *peasant*, but this term, although it depends on this language, is often foreign to the peasantry itself. It is how they are identified yet there are other names according to the time period and their activities: farmers, day workers, tenants, landlords, ploughman, land workers, etc. But what do they call themselves? Almost always, external observers have referred to them differently to what they call themselves, whether they come from urban, scientific or political sectors. The Spanish denomination of "campesino" (peasant), for example, as common as it is in urban, political and scientific contexts, is distinct from the diverse and objective ways the peasants call themselves. They call themselves "labradores": those who plough. Yet a whole host of other terms are also employed: Labregos, lavradores, llauradors, pagès, paisano, peasant, pessant. We dare not attempt to distinguish them in a universal and timeless way, so many years after T. Shanin classified this as a supremely difficult task in

²⁵ BAROJA, Julio Caro. *Le Carnaval*. Trad. Sylvie Sesé Léger. Paris, Gallimard, 1979.

his important article published in 1979, "Defining Peasants".²⁶ But we know that peasants were defined in different ways in the past, which has left traces and sources that allow us to study them and not just the images of them left by ecclesiastic and aristocratic sources.

Finally, it is necessary that we mention the historiographical currents of the *Annales*, who were among the great promoters of the insertion of the peasantry in history, even before World War II: from Marc Bloch to George Lefebvre, who stressed the peasantry as an essential agent in the origins of the French revolution to G. Duby's studies on the medieval peasantry in the early 1960s.²⁷ The lessons, methods and investigations of Bloch and Lucien Febvre in the 1920s are well integrated within current rural and agrarian global studies as the contributors to this edition of *Workers of the World* amply demonstrate. Other authors cited in this edition, such as Scott, Thompson and Shanin, are incorporated into some of the articles that, without quoting them, include the extent of their conceptual knowledge in practical terms; they have incorporated them as if they were a light rain, falling upon the current scholars of the history of the peasantry and its conflicts.

It is also possible to ascertain, in the works gathered here, how the old dichotomies regarding the peasantry (pre-political versus political, modern versus primitive) can be overcome. There is also a need for a more open and plural interpretation, less sociological than the characterizations of B. Moore and T. Skocpol in political science that were so successful in their day. An interpretation that pays closer attention to historical change in a world where change is more common than during the postwar and Cold War eras is therefore necessary. Moreover, after post modernism and the linguistic turn in historiography, a return to the material and the social is as appreciated as it is necessary. It is essential that we bring in, syncretically but eclectically, the methodological and theoretical innovations that have been produced, tested and incorporated in recent decades. It remains the case that using the definition of the peasant without succumbing to ahistorical essentialisms and at the same time being able to incorporate their internal diversity and the multiple local realities (sometimes even within the same country) nevertheless continues to be a challenge.

The eagerness to continue such critical research on the peasantry had been clear since the fall of 2013 when the Histagra research group discussed its call for papers that resulted in this issue of *Workers of the World*. We decided to suggest a number of principal themes or lines of research that the authors could consider as a guide to formalize their proposals. Starting off from an inclusive and global perspective, the six main themes of the issue would be the following:

- Theoretical, methodological and historiographical reflections on the

²⁶ SHANIN, T. "Defining Peasants: Conceptualisation and De-conceptualisations, Old and New in a Marxist Debate". *Peasant Studies*. vol. 8, n. 4, 1979, pp. 38-60.

²⁷ BLOCH, M. *Les caracteres originaux de l'histoire rurale française*. Paris: A. Colin, 1952 ; LEFEBVRE, G.. *La Révolution Française*. Paris : Presses universitaires de France, 1951 ; DUBY, G.. *L'économie rurale et la vie des campagnes dans l'Occident médiéval*. Paris, Aubier, 1962.

peasant (with all his/her heterogeneity) as a historical subject.

- The conflict between the environmental and the productive. The control and management of productive resources at the heart of the conflict (fiscal, environmental, productive, etc.) in rural areas.

- Ownership, possession and struggle for land, paying particular attention to common peoples.

- The juxtaposition of rural and urban identity, and their multiple forms of expression (in cultural, social or technological contexts).

- The role of peasant societies in the shaping and transformation of the major contemporary political systems and ideologies: liberalism; fascism; socialism; democracy.

- Emigration and conflicts over land.

The time has now come for a brief critical assessment of the responses we received in regard to our proposal to reinterpret rural conflicts in the contemporary world. We begin with a presentation of what the readers will find in this monograph, and we will leave the synthetic diagnosis of the combined contributions to the end. It should be obvious that, among the six themes we mentioned, there are numerous points of contact or, in other words, most of the dozen articles that were chosen may, without much difficulty, be ascribed to two or three of the suggested thematic blocks. We will move from the themes with the least response to the ones with the greatest.

As was somewhat predictable, the texts built around a theoretical/methodological reflection are a minority, which is not to say that the other contributions do not include valuable observations on this topic. Only the piece by Eric Vanhaute: “Globalizing local struggles – Localizing global struggles. Peasant movements from local to global platforms and back again” takes on this perspective, by comparing a current peasant movement (*La Via Campesina*), and its practices of resistance, with examples from the past, while presenting the current peasant movements as proactive towards the future, and not simply as a defensive response to threats such as environmental degradation and risks as well as the role of multinationals in the control of production and of agricultural markets at a global level. The theoretical debate between the environmentalists and the institutionalists also has a very important place in David Soto's text “Community, institutions and environment in conflicts over common lands in Galicia, NW Spain (18th - 20th centuries)”.

The conflict of identities (rural and urban) did not attract much attention from the contributions incorporated into this number either. Peasant identities seep into every text, historically manifesting themselves in a number of different ways, depending on the discourse of the various social groups that make up the peasantry as they define, construct and reshape the context of the political conflicts related to the demand for or access to land. But they almost always appear as an ingredient (almost naturalized) of what is

explained and not as an object of study in itself.

In this regard, we would like to draw attention to the text of Domenico Perrotta and Devi Saccheto “Migrant farmworkers in Southern Italy: ghettos, *caporalato* and collective action”, that explores the working conditions of illegal immigrants from Africa (North Africans and sub-Saharan Africans) in the agro-industrial crop farms in southern Italy from a methodological perspective that is halfway between sociology and anthropology. Their work shows how new social and work identities are created in a rural world replete with acute productive and territorial transformations. Simultaneously, previous labour and social identities from the old system of large land-holdings, such as the *caporali* or gangmasters (which functioned as intermediaries between illegal workers and agricultural employers), were reactivated in the "new" stage of capitalist industrial agriculture. Moreover, this article aims to examine the relations between migration and new forms of conflict.

If there is a "classic" theme in agrarian historiography (from the French Revolution to the Landless Workers' Movement) it is the matter of the access to land by different groups of the peasantry of rural societies, usually highly stratified. Processes such as the vindication of the access of peasants to the exploitation of natural resources, the protection of the common lands and the aim of becoming individual owners have almost always unfolded against the background of social and political conflicts that were explicit, latent, and long-term, with peaks of intensity associated with certain historical conjunctures. Several of the articles in this issue can be inserted into this thematic line: it is the case with the works of Carlos Humberto Durand Alcántara “Hegemony, agrarian problem and Indian peoples in Mexico (A legal perspective)” and Noemí Girbal-Blacha “Land conflicts in Formosa. Argentina (1884-1958)”. The contributions of Massimo Asta and Niccolò Mignemi, discussed later in this introduction, may also be included in this theme.

Durand Alcántara examines the historical process of the establishment of agrarian property in Mexico and its relation to the Mexican Revolution and to the intervention of the indigenous peoples as well as the United States. From a legal perspective, the author contrasts the myth of agrarian reform, the totem of the post-revolutionary *ejido* (communal land), with a detailed study of this historical process that is the key to understanding the creation of contemporary Mexican identity. The text by Girbal-Blancha is a good example of the relationship between the two historical processes: the colonization and shaping of the land in South America, taking as an example the case of the province of Formosa (in north-eastern Argentina) and exploring the social unrest arising from this process.

The articles of Massimo Asta “Between “resistance” to the war and social conflict. Revolts and “peasant republics” in southern Italy, 1943-1945” and Niccolò Mignemi “Peasant cooperatives and land occupations in the Sicilian *latifundium* (1944-1950)” look into very similar geographic areas and agrarian systems (southern mainland Italy and Sicily) with a certain chronological (and historical) proximity. Asta analyzes the events that occurred after the liberation of southern Italy from the Nazi occupation. The

emergence of "peasant republics", their claim for immediate access and ownership of the land in a very specific historical moment, and the different discourses (and ways of thinking) in relation to land occupations actually put peasant communities in conflict with left-wing political organizations. Meanwhile, Mignemi also addresses land claims in post-war Sicily, explaining the (partial) distribution of the land of large estates among agricultural workers and small subsistence farmers. In the social conflict around the demands for access to land by the aforementioned groups, he highlights the role played by agricultural cooperatives and their multifunctional nature. Both texts fit not only in the aforementioned thematic lines, but also in a unique and very complex political process: the political and social reconstruction of Italy after the defeat of fascism.

The texts by Mignemi and Asta are not the only ones that may be paired up. The contributions by Cristian Ferrer "Popular empowerment, peasant struggles and political change: Southern Catalonia under late Francoism (1968-1976)" and María Candelaria Fuentes Navarro "The Spanish Communist Party and the Andalusian countryside. Rural mobilization and social empowerment (1956-1979)" address a common time period: the last years of Francoism and the transition to democracy and, above all, they do so from a detailed perspective within the context of current Spanish historiography on the rural world in this period. Ferrer studies an example of fiscal conflict in southern Catalonia as a mechanism for the social and political articulation of the anti-Franco opposition in a rural area, integrating the values and forms of protest characteristic of the peasantry. This perspective of social mobilization from below is also present (at least partially) in the article by Candelaria Fuentes Navarro, who illustrates the success of the Communist Party of Spain (PCE) in the anti-Franco agrarian mobilization in Andalusia, understanding all the protests as a process of education in democratization.

Finally, we feature three texts that revolve around different manifestations of rural unrest, though in very different historical contexts. Picking up the thread of fiscal unrest, the work of Héctor J. Martínez Covaleta, "Peasants and the revolution of 1781 in the viceroyalty of New Granada (Colombia)" studies peasant revolts of an anti-fiscal nature, undertaking a critical analysis of them and presenting a new multi-causal interpretation, more attentive to the importance of "popular" elements. This text, in addition to the contribution of David Soto, is one that clearly shows the chronology of a conflict that occurred before the twentieth century. Edouard Lynch, in "The fight against multiple professional land holdings: a new agrarian issue during France's "silent revolution" (1950-1970)" analyses the effects caused by the process of accelerated agrarian modernization in the French rural world during the post-war period of 1950-1980. The author discusses the forms of protest in the French rural world and the interaction between the discontents of the farmers with that of other social groups. The contribution of Pedro Gabriel Silva "Political opportunity and collective mobilization in post-revolutionary Portugal – the case of a socio-environmental conflict in the Portuguese inland (1974-1980)" studies, with the conceptual tools of the theory of collective action and social mobilization, the socio-environmental conflict caused by the exploitation of an open pit mine in the Portuguese town of Gaia, in a very particular sociopolitical context, that of the years of upheaval and reorganization of the political and institutional spheres that

followed the Portuguese Revolution of 1974. Together with an anthropological perspective, which in turn leads to constant reconstruction of the identities in the transforming rural communities, the author also addresses factors such as memory and perception. This text and the one by David Soto are the articles that clearly incorporate an environmental perspective into this issue.

A quick look at the texts as a whole brings up a series of questions that illustrate some of the possible weaknesses of this special issue. Even though this was not the wish of the editors, we found ourselves with an issue much more Eurocentric than we wanted. Putting aside the introduction for a while, this monograph has twelve articles, of which at least 8 (or 66%) focus on the examination of European case studies, with an absolute predominance of what we might call Mediterranean (Western, specifically) Europe: three contributions on South Italy; three others look into various “regional” examples in Spain; one article on Portugal and another on France. There are no contributions on Eastern or Central Europe, Scandinavia or Great Britain. Three other items were on Latin America (Colombia, Argentina and Mexico), representing 25% of the articles. We received no articles that had Asia or Africa as their object of study, even though these are continents where the peasantry is, to date, the majority of the population, both in absolute terms (as a workforce) and in terms of analysis, the active population as the peasantry in these continents was, as stated above, central to the theoretical and methodological renewal of history and social sciences over the past half century in terms of the approach to the rural world as an object of study.

Moreover, the chronological concentration of the pieces is noteworthy. Few assumed a historical study with a wide time frame, only the articles by David Soto and, to a lesser extent, Noemí Girbal. By contrast, half of the work is restricted to a very specific stage, the long post-World War II period that for the purposes of this dossier begins in 1943 (if we start from the Mezzogiorno) to 1980 (ending with the "wave of democratization" that engulfed the countries of the Iberian Peninsula). We might even make more restrictive chronological groupings in the articles of this edition: the period immediately after the war and the transitions from dictatorship to democracy in the 1970s. As has been previously mentioned in this introduction, many of our studies are still children of a post-war period and modernity that we have yet to explain and understand, in order to comprehend ourselves better.

In any case, the twentieth century acts as a chronological marker for the majority of the articles, with exceptional approaches to the chronological borders of the contemporary stage, whether it be from the bottom (the end of the eighteenth century) or from the top, as is the case with the contributions which are related to the present. Our invitation, despite the “contemporary” priority we wanted to give in this monograph, for works focused on the rural conflicts in the Old World or in the Middle Ages, continuously re-examined and interpreted by the Agrarian history of the present, did not have the resonance we thought it deserved.

Finally, we found that, among all the articles we received, some very important themes were missing: none of the proposals we received attempted to examine rural

conflicts from a gender studies perspective. No attention was paid to another of the agents of social and cultural transformation, one that is most characteristic of the rural world: youth. Indigenous people were largely ignored (with some exceptions), as well as their relation to the environment and to agricultural practices. We also noted the absence of a closer approach to the urban-rural interaction and to the “market” (in a broad sense) as the point of interconnection – often of conflict – between producers, consumers and intermediaries. Lastly, it is surprising that with the current agenda so full of questions regarding the environmental viability of the planet in the medium term, the relation between this and food production, the use of finite natural resources and land management – all themes in which the rural world will play a determinant role – were barely present in the proposals we received.

In any case, the distance between the proposal made at the time by the editors of this special issue of *Workers of the World* and the specific contributions received may be associated with a wide range of factors: the novelty factor of the journal itself; the type of academic circles where it is better known (most likely among Europeans); the fact that the labour movement and urban workers have, so far, been the primary object of study, especially in comparison with other types of workers (rural) more heterogeneous and difficult to characterize; and the historiographical impact of the conflicts throughout the twentieth century compared to other historical periods, etc.